

Acoustic Levitation

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The article discusses the difference between flying and levitation using acoustic levitation as an example. For this purpose, a concrete levitation experiment with ultrasound is performed and described in order to relate it to the history of knowledge of acoustic levitation. In doing so, the question of the materiality of sound serves as a central argument.

Two Different Experiments?

Rummelsburg, Berlin. 15 Nöldnerstraße. The facade is in the typical style of the *Gründerzeit*, but there is a 38-metres tall brick tower rising up from the centre of the plot. In 1901, the property was taken over by the Juhl & Söhne Lead Foundry and Machine Factory, which built this tower a few years later to manufacture lead shot. Following an English patent from 1782 mentioned by Lipscombe and Mungan (2012), drops of molten lead were allowed to drip from the tower. The effect is twofold. First, if one let's a drop of lead fall down, then the falling movement is accelerated exactly by the measure of the earth's gravity. Hence, the drop lives at least for a short time in a world, where no gravitational force exists. Instead, only the surface tension of the lead acts, which is why the typical stretched drop shape changes into a more or less perfect sphere. Second, the lead cools, such that shot maintains its spherical form after the fall and can indeed be fished out of a basin of water waiting below – which is exactly what they were after in Rummelsburg.

Xi'an, Northwestern Polytechnical University. A typical laboratory in the Department of Applied Physics, where in 2006 experiments are being conducted on the levitation of objects “without material contact” (Xie et al., 2006, p. 1).¹ The group around W. J. Xie is working with ultrasound, i. e. it appears as if gravity has been overcome, because we don't see any physical contact or direct exertion of force: “Although the acoustic radiation pressure is negligible as compared with the sound pressure and the atmosphere pressure, it provides the levitation force to counteract the gravity.” (*Ibid.*, p. 1) Not only the experimenters have this impression, so do the objects of the experiment, including in this case an ant that is desperately trying to run away: “Sometimes, it struggled to escape from the constraint of acoustic

¹ The technical details of this experiment had already been published some years previously under Xie and Wei (2001).

radiation force by rapidly flexing its legs. However, it failed because its legs can obtain little counterforce from the air.” (Xie et al., 2006, p. 1)

The ant survives the 30-minute presentation unscathed; a small fish, in an equivalent experiment, does not. Although it swims through a weightless world almost as usual, it lacks the oxygen of the water in this artificial environment. Since the question of artificial environments does not seem to be of any importance for the physicists, this experimental setting at Northwestern Polytechnical University is rather reminiscent of a nineteenth-century magic show – especially as the publication lacks a clear scientific question. Nevertheless, viewed from a cultural studies perspective, the experiment by Xie et al. does pose a remarkable problem: Why does the magical impression arise that gravity has been suspended, even though it is simultaneously clear that the experiment is based on a material interaction, that is to say, it is precisely not contact-free as Xie et al. are claiming? Or to put it differently: What exactly is the difference between a shot tower and the ant experiment?²

To approach this question, I will first return to the shot tower, this time from the perspective of physics. The laws of physics are, unlike cultural practices, literally universal. They must be valid everywhere, in every conceivable world. Such that, as Albert Einstein deduced from this axiom in 1907, when an observer in a closed room cannot decide whether an object is falling because the earth is pulling on it or because the room is being hastened upward by a hidden lifting mechanism, this is not due to the incompetence of the observer, but is instead a physical principle. This so-called equivalence principle is the epistemic basis of the General Theory of Relativity and indeed of the experimental possibility of switching off gravity with the help of a drop tower.

How can we imagine a world without gravitation?³ How can weightlessness be produced? The first option is to accelerate an artificial environment in such a way that the acceleration precisely suspends gravity (or, more precisely – *is* gravity, according to Einstein). The second option is to induce standing waves – but do they really suspend gravity? We thus have the two experimental settings described at the outset and the epistemic question arising from this, why these two phenomena, which from a physical perspective are so different, can intermingle in acoustic levitation. Or, to put it a little more straightforward: Why do we believe that gravitation is suspended just because we do not observe any material interaction? I believe that an answer to this question leads us closer to the epistemic problem of what sound is, that is to say, the question of what comprises its material dimension, which is perpetually being overlaid with the aesthetic-symbolic level.

Standing Waves

Sound as a medium exists only because there is gravitation. Gravitation produces a dense, compressible field of air – our atmosphere. This is, as no Science Fiction film can resist reminding us, why it is completely silent in outer space.⁴ Before this backdrop, the concept of acoustic levitation seems to be paradoxical: Sound is used to suspend gravitation, the

² In Kassung, 2023, I examine the same question from a more cultural studies perspective.

³ Cf. the concept of physical worlds in <http://cube-of-physics.org>.

⁴ Cf. i. e. the discussions on the director's cut of Alfonso Cuarón's 2013 movie "Gravity".

very force or field which is its own condition? That would amount to a sort of negative *Münchhausen* effect.

In order to pursue this question of the materiality of sound more intensively, in the following I would like to take the double path of theory and practice.⁵ Following the progress of a concrete experiment on acoustic levitation step-by-step, I will call up the physical knowledge, as well as the history of that knowledge, on which each step is based. The aim is to thus enable a discussion of the entanglement of the material and symbolic levels at which sound events may have a cultural effect.

Figure 1: First experimental setup.

The experiment follows a set of instructions published by Ulrich Schmerold in April 2018 in the magazine “Make:” (cf. Schmerold, 2018), and can thus be seen in the context of the maker and fab lab movement (cf. Walter-Herrmann and Büching, 2013). As mentioned above, the experiment takes place within the gravitational field of earth, which is to say within the atmosphere produced by the gravitation of earth’s mass. Air – a material layer of different gases surrounding the Earth – can be compressed, and then it has the tendency to return to a state of equilibrium. This provides the fundamental condition for an oscillating system: pressure distribution in the sound field is dependent on place and time. The two components are linked, which is precisely why information can also be transmitted with the help of sound.

Now, within an oscillating system, the same state is reached again after time T (with frequency f) and after distance λ , which is also called phase velocity c :

$$c = \frac{\lambda}{T} = \lambda f. \quad (1)$$

For the amplitude of a simple wave

$$A(x, t) = A_0 \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}t - \frac{2\pi}{\lambda}x\right) = A_0 \cos(\omega t - kx) \quad (2)$$

⁵ With special thanks to Jann Mausen, who carried out a large part of the 2019 experiments as part of the Temporary Object Laboratory at the Hermann von Helmholtz-Zentrum für Kulturtechnik/Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin.

this means that the wave expands along the x-axis at phase velocity $c = \omega/k$.

Given this physical background, we can right jump into the experimental setup. To produce such a propagating sound wave, we are using the KPUS-40T-16R-K768 ultrasonic transmitter. According to its [datasheet](#), this transmitter has a vibration frequency of (40 ± 1) kHz. We generate the signal for operating the transmitter with an Arduino Nano clocked at 16 MHz (cf. [roboromania.ro](#)). Reduced by a factor of 200, we end up with an 80 kHz square signal or a full wave cycling at 40 kHz at the analog ports. Since the transmitter can be operated with a maximum of 20 V, but the maximum output voltage of the Arduino is only 5 V, we amplify the signal with a stepper driver based on the L298N chip (cf. [www.instructables.com](#)).

Figure 2: Transmitter signal (CH1) and Arduino output (CH2).

Figure 3: Fast Fourier Transformation of transmitter signal.

To verify what we have achieved by this experimental setup, we monitor the transmitter's input signal together with its output sound signal on the oscilloscope using a simple voltage divider circuit (cf. figure 2): The first channel shows the sinusoidal waveform of the sound signal captured by the cermet microphone and the second channel the square wave of the Arduino/stepper output. Of course, the ultrasonic signal produced by the transmitter is much more complex than the input signal: We don't merely 'hear' a signal, but an acoustic sensation that becomes louder and quieter, changing its pitch and timbre. One can decompose the signal using the oscilloscope's Fast Fourier Transformation (cf. figure 3). Hence, within this setup, a complex, temporally variable air compression travels with phase velocity c from transmitter to microphone. This is however precisely what we don't want: any transmission of information. For if a sound event transmits certain sonic information, then it will also not be possible to immobilize an object in this sound field – against the effect of gravity. Hence, the phase velocity c should equal zero. Just a tone, a sine wave as pure as possible standing in the room and thus creating an artificial environment.

Although communication is based on propagating waves, standing waves are fundamental. A sound cannot be generated any other way than by causing a spatially limited object to oscillate (cf. Orear, 1982, pp. 474–475). The string of a violin, for example, cannot oscillate at the two suspension points because it is fixed at them. An organ pipe presents the exact

opposite scenario: the oscillation is generated at the labium and forms an antinode there and – at least in open pipes – at the end of the pipe body. A spatially fixed distribution of nodes and antinodes is thus generated, with the effect that the acoustic force – i. e. sound pressure – on particles is always exerted in the direction of the nodes.

Figure 4: Producing a standing wave.

An ultrasonic transmitter’s mechanism of sound generation is fundamentally different, however. Piezoelectric crystals are made to oscillate by applying an alternating voltage, and the oscillations are then mechanically amplified.⁶ The crystal translates the electric oscillation pattern into a sound field, but without actively oscillating itself as a mechanical system. Standing waves can thus only be generated by a trick in which one superimposes the same oscillation, but with the inverse direction of propagation. This can be achieved by reflection against a hard medium or, as in our case, simply with a second transmitter. Expressed in the language of mathematics, this means adding a second waveform with negative wave vector k :

$$A(x, t) = A_0 \cos(\omega t - kx) + A_0 \cos(\omega t + kx) \quad (3)$$

Applying an addition theorem to this results in:

$$A(x, t) = -2A_0 \cos(\omega t) \cos(kx) \quad (4)$$

The decisive aspect of this formula is that spatial and temporal components are no longer linked. There is a time-dependent part $\cos(\omega t)$ that is the same for all positions. And there is a position-dependent part $\cos(kx)$ that is the same for all times. The wave thus oscillates temporally, but precisely so that at any given point, the wave alternates between its least and

⁶ Piezoelectricity was discovered by Pierre and Jacques Curie in 1880, but it was not until the end of World War I that it was used technically to detect enemy submarines. Cf. J. Curie and P. Curie, 1880 and Manbachi and Cobbold, 2011.

greatest value at that point. Correspondingly, there are spots at intervals of $\lambda/2$, where the amplitude always equals zero or is always maximal: we have achieved a standing wave.

Theory and Practice

This knowledge was first put to deliberate use by August Kundt in 1866 in order to visualize sound waves: “Dust-figures made by sounding air masses, inside an organ pipe for instance, have yet to be observed.” (Kundt, 1866, p. 498) For, unlike Chladni’s figures, the “new dust-figures” (*ibid.*, p. 499) are created directly by standing air waves inside a glass tube, this setup allowed an immediate reading of the wavelength and from it a calculation of the speed of sound c in air, which is what Kundt was originally after. Putting this to the test, Kundt found that if the tube was evacuated, the dust-figures failed to form (*cf. ibid.*, p. 501).

Now, with regard to the cork dust visualizing the standing wave in Kundt’s pipe, an important distinction comes into play. So far, we have only talked about the so-called far field, which is the area that is relatively far away from the sound source and can be described quite easily with the above mentioned mathematics. It’s the wave pattern that is formed by the dust particles. However, within this far field perspective, nothing is said about the cork’s specific movement. In 1884, the English physicist Lord Rayleigh published a first mathematical explanation of these oscillatory phenomena, in which he described acoustic radiation pressure as a nonlinear effect, i. e. the near field of the stationary air vortex (*cf. Rayleigh, 1902, 1905; Rayleigh, 1884*). Here, mathematics gets very complicated. In this essay, all nonlinear effects beyond the individual levitation zones are simply ignored (*cf. Whymark, 1975, p. 252*).

Figure 5: Bücks/Müller 1933: Alcohol mist in standing wave.

Before we return to the experiment and to the generation of a standing ultrasound wave, we must clear up the question of when and why Kundt’s dust tube was tilted into a vertical position, i. e. of how acoustic levitation emerged from the observation of fascinating dust patterns. An important intermediate step was taken by the Breslau physicists Karl Bücks and Hans Müller in 1933 (*cf. Bücks and Müller, 1933*). Their work was based on the use of extremely thin platinum wires to measure standing waves. Owing to their velocity dis-

tribution, the air particles have a varying cooling effect on the preheated wire, allowing its resistance change to be used to determine wavelength (cf. Müller and Kraefft, 1932). The point was thus “to investigate more precisely the acoustic field produced by piezo quartz crystals; the spatial velocity distribution was to be determined in both standing and traveling waves, primarily with hot-wires.” (Bücks and Müller, 1933, p. 75) In addition, tobacco smoke and alcohol fog were used to make the air currents visible, taking the whole experimental system in the direction of a wind tunnel (cf. Kassung, 2018). Incidentally, as it were, “one drop forms in each of the velocity antinodes. They reach a diameter of up to 1 mm and remain suspended until they evaporate after 1 to 2 minutes.” (Bücks and Müller, 1933, p. 80) The paragraph in which the standing wave is measured ends with a sentence that is decisive for our purposes here:

The fact that the alcohol droplets are kept floating against the force of gravity is to be explained by the action of ponderomotive forces. (*Ibid.*, pp. 81–82)

We thus note that acoustic levitation was technically realized at Waetzmann’s Physikalisches Institut in Breslau as early as the 1930s, but that it did not constitute an epistemically relevant phenomenon. The sound field of a piezo quartz was visualized and measured but without the question of the relation between gravitation and sound field, or its potential technological relevance, even coming up.

Figure 6: Whymark 1975: The energy well leviator.

In an approximately contemporaneous publication by Louis V. King from McGill University, we find the first indication of a vertical alignment of the sound field:

Of some interest from the experimental point of view is the possibility of suspending small spherical particles against gravity in a vertical column of fluid in which supersonic stationary waves are generated by a piezo-electric oscillator. (King, 1934, pp. 236–237)

However, upon calculating the energy required for the levitation of small pellets of cork, King came to the sobering conclusion that “even at supersonic frequencies the velocity amplitude required is much beyond that experimentally realizable.” (King, 1934, p. 237) So while the physicists at McGill in Canada were able to calculate the nonlinear effects in a standing ultrasound field, but considered acoustic levitation to be (technologically) not yet realizable, in Breslau the first particles were in fact already being levitated in the form of alcohol droplets – albeit without further mathematical or technical interest. This means that we are clearly dealing with an epistemic object that shuttles indecisively back and forth between theory and practice and is unable to stabilize itself as a reliable technology or as formal knowledge: (cf. Rheinberger, 2006, pp. 20–34) “The suspension of small particles and bubbles against gravity in a vertical stationary radiation field is discussed.” (King, 1934, p. 240)

If we make a jump now to the year of 1975, acoustic levitation appears as a technically stable thing: “The non-contact positioning of materials in a space processing chamber is accomplished using a new type of acoustic levitator.” (Whymark, 1975, p. 251) Suddenly, everything seems possible: Things can be levitated without contact at any position of the room, they can be melted there and also solidify again. However – and this brings us back to the shot tower and ant of our opening scene – Roy Whymark’s article displaces the laboratory into outer space, because there, the sound field has less influence on the material processes of the sample: “The acoustic field strengths can be reduced and thereby further reduce the effects of these fields upon the material being processed.” (Ibid., p. 251)

Accordingly, Whymark now conceives of the levitation process as also completely independent of the orientation of the sound field in space, or relative to the gravitational field: “Levitation is position-stable and independent of the orientation of the sound beam.” (Ibid., p. 255) For acoustic levitation, the gravitational field no longer has any influence on the position of the sample object in space, although it certainly does impact the material processes within the sample (cf. Trinh, 1985). If these processes are not important, i. e. if we find ourselves in the milieu of the maker scene’s demonstration experiments, the suspicion that gravity has somehow been suspended automatically comes to the fore.

With that, back to our own experiment. For excitation we use not a violin bow like Kundt, but an Arduino to which are attached two ultrasonic transmitters of the aforementioned type KPUS-40T-16R-K768. They oscillate in phase, thus generating identical sound signals. Now, if the two transmitters are arranged in opposite directions along the same axis, the signals overlap as calculated in equation 4. To achieve the maximum effect, the sound path must be made to resonate: wave crests must collide with wave crests. For this we adjust the distance between the two transmitters until the square signal of the Arduino and the signal received from one of the two ultrasonic transmitters are exactly in phase in the oscilloscope, see figure 8.

If this is the case, the distance d between the two transmitters is exactly one integer multiple of half the wavelength. We can thus calculate d with an assumed speed of sound in air of 343,2 m/s at 20 °C:

$$d = k \cdot \frac{\lambda}{2} = k \cdot \frac{c}{2f} = k \cdot \frac{343,2 \text{ m/s}}{2 \cdot 40 \text{ kHz}} = 4,3 \text{ mm} \quad (5)$$

Figure 7: Close up of the experimental setup.

According to far-field theory, the distance between two wave nodes is equal to half the wavelength. In figure 7 we measure a distance of 9,0 mm for an entire wavelength, which yields a sound velocity c of

$$c = \lambda f = 9,0 \text{ mm} \cdot 40 \text{ kHz} = 360,0 \text{ m/s} \quad (6)$$

which is in astonishing agreement with the literature value of 343,2 m/s (measurement error 4,9 %). The distance of ca. 4,5 mm between two wave nodes of course also means that any sample object – in addition to having a very low weight – must be of dimensions small enough to permit it even being positioned in a wave trough. In this regard, styrofoam pellets with an diameter of ca. 1,5 mm proved ideal for the experiment: owing to its wavelength, ultrasound interacts best with styrofoam. The pellets just rest stable in the wave nodes without any rotational or trembling near-field interaction.

If we now disrupt the sound field slightly by moving a reflective object close to the acoustic axis, we can also change the position of the particles horizontally. Of course this only works within very narrow limits, until the field collapses; but it makes clear that a sound field can of course also be constructed as a fully three-dimensional formation. The sound field thus has the same properties as a hologram, which permits an almost arbitrary manipulation of objects in space, from the microscopic to the macroscopic (cf. Rieger and Schröter, 2009). This is also the direction in which experiments in acoustic levitation are currently moving, for example in order to develop spatial sieve and filter configurations for the tiniest objects (cf. Li et al., 2014; Marzo et al., 2015). Even in the Maker scene, there are now first projects in which an array of wave nodes is built (cf. <https://www.instructables.com>).

Within this relatively stable far-field configuration, it is of course also possible to obtain some evidence of the near-field. If i. e. an irregularly formed styrofoam probe is introduced to the sound field, it is fixed by the far field at a node position as before. But we additionally observe, that the object rotates on account of the nonlinear circulations in the near field. If

Figure 8: Oscilloscope screen with Arduino output (CH1) and sound capture (CH2) in phase.

we also reduce the voltage to the piezo crystals, the far field remains stable until the probe becomes too heavy, whereas the effect of the near field becomes increasingly stronger: The styrofoam probe gets into a tumbling motion. Of course, all these parameters can be modified in a targeted way to generate a more effective levitation force, but that would divert from the actual topic of this essay (cf. Xie and Wei, 2001).

Magic und Materiality

Let's return once more from these increasingly complex configurations of the sound field to the simple starting situation of our experiment. With a wire spoon, we very carefully lay a styrofoam sphere into a wave node. There it is seized by an invisible hand: It seems to be possible to touch something without touching it. With acoustic tweezers, the materiality of sound becomes immediately visible through the timeaxis manipulation of a standing wave (cf. Kittler, 1990). What we have before us is material interaction, just as if we were holding the styrofoam sphere with *proper* tweezers. But then where does the suspicion of magic come from, or, to put it somewhat less polemically: How can we explain the fascination with levitation?

Although magicians have perfected tricks to demonstrate seemingly free floatation of objects and parapsychologists investigate levitation claimed to have been caused by supernatural mental forces, physicists have studied a series of effects that allow true levitation of solid and even liquid matter. (Brandt, 1989, p. 349)

Put differently, 'true levitation' is based precisely not on the suspension of gravity but on the establishment of a static sound field that interacts materially with the sample object. But why, to return to our initial question, does this interaction also gets ignored epistemically

on account of its invisibility? Why is gravitation instead magically suspended, as it is by the equivalence principle in the shot tower?

Any answer to this question must necessarily be speculative or point to a broader cultural and historical context. It should first of all be noted that levitation always has had the power to evoke extreme fascination, whether in the context of religion or magic, from Matthew's report of Jesus' walking on water to the Scottish psychokineticist Danial Dunglas Home in the nineteenth-century and today's street performers roosting for hours in pedestrian zones on their concealed perches. Simply because we do not recognize the mechanism, we *want* to attribute the effect to gravity or its suspension because this activates a stable, even if paranormal, interpretative frame.

Figure 9: Poster advertising Modern Witchery at the Egyptian Hall, London Piccadilly, est. 1894.

Against this background, one common feature stands out between all these examples: Levitation is stationary movement. There seems to be a fundamental difference between levitation and flight. With flying, the propulsion or mechanism of action is immediately visible as fast movement. Gravity is compensated by an internal mechanism and an active force. With levitation, on the other hand, we do not see these connections. Everything seems to be at rest, not based on pure mechanics, but on magical suspension of gravity. Angels do not fly as well as the virgin made to hover by John Maskelyne (cf. Dawes, 1979, p. 164). We remain within this epistemic constellation when we observe the styrofoam spheres in the sound field.

This argumentation leads to the further question of why the mechanism of sound is not recognized. We don't see sound of course, but the tactile perception of sound as agitated air is ubiquitous. Yet – and this point seems to be decisive to me – sound is perceived predominantly as a transmission medium and not as a storage medium: If we constantly communi-

cate by sound, how is anything supposed to be fixed in a sound wave? We must additionally consider how the increasing technological entanglement of acoustic and electromagnetic transmissions since the end of the nineteenth century has caused the materiality of sound to progressively yield the limelight to sound's symbolic dimension. Sound today is, put succinctly, what we hear and not how we hear. But sound is an eminently wilful, materially based medium.

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